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and functions in context
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List of acronyms and abbreviations

WP	Work Package
EU	European Union
LTES	Long-Term Experiments

1. Introduction

The objective of Work Package 4 (WP4) within the MINOTAUR project is to validate selected soil biodiversity indicators and models, examining their sensitivity and ranges concerning soil type, climate, and management practices—collectively referred to as context scenarios. By addressing these variables, WP4 aims to fill existing knowledge gaps, gather additional information on specific understudied parameters, and validate the indicators identified in Work Package 3 (WP3) and provide data to parameterize and validate models developed in Work Package 5 (WP5). This will be achieved through targeted measurements and new empirical data obtained from three primary sources: Long-Term Experiments (LTEs) (Task 4.1), laboratory incubations (Task 4.2), and archived chronosequences (Task 4.3) (Figure 1). The simultaneous analysis of biodiversity indicators and functions under identical scenarios will enhance our understanding of the covariation between diversity and function, potentially leading to the development of novel multi-taxa indicators.

The impetus for WP4 stems from previous and ongoing initiatives, such as those by Orgiazzi et al. (2016), the Global Soil Biodiversity Initiative (Guerra et al., 2020), and activities within the EJP-SOIL program (Pavlu et al., 2021). These efforts have identified commonly used indicators for soil biodiversity; however, the variability and ranges of these indicators in relation to climate, soil types, and soil management practices remain insufficiently understood. Additionally, the relationships between biodiversity, soil functioning, and ecosystem services across varying European edaphoclimatic and management gradients have yet to be comprehensively elucidated (Delgado-Baquerizo et al., 2020).

Figure 1. General approach of WP4 to obtain empirical measurements of soil biodiversity indicator and soil functions under various context scenarios.

2. Long Tem Experiments (LTEs) and experimental design

We have assessed a comprehensive list of bioindicators (both taxonomical and functional) and related soil functions on nine selected LTEs (Figure 2) that have been running by consortium partner institutions for more than a decade and include a minimum of three randomized blocks. These selected LTEs encompass a large gradient of edapho-climatic conditions and are located across eight countries, namely Spain, France, Italy, Slovenia, Austria, Switzerland, The Netherlands, and Sweden. All experiments asses the effects of minimizing soil disturbance by comparing standard tillage vs. reduced or no-tillage and/or implementing distinct fertilization approaches (mineral vs. organic amendments; Table 1).

Figure 2. Location of the sampled LTEs, managed by partner institutions within the MINOTAUR Project

Table 1. LTEs selected for Task 4.1 and their experimental design: Fertilization treatments include mineral (MN), organic (OG) and non-fertilized (NF). The type of organic fertilization is shown. Cultivation treatments include Standard or conventional tillage (ST), reduced tillage (RT) and no tillage or direct seeding (NT). The numbers indicate tillage depth

LTE - Experimental site	Country	Partner	Fertilization			Cultivation		
			MN	OG	NF	ST	RT	NT
SOERE-PRO-EFELE-TS-MO	France	ACO	X	Cattle manure		22	8	
FAST	Switzerland	AGS	X	Cattle slurry		20	8	0
Hollabrunn	Austria	BOKU	X			20	8	0
Fagna	Italy	CREA	X			40	12	
La Canaleja	Spain	INIA	X	Poultry manure		25	20	0
Uppsala research station (Säby)	Sweden	SLU	X			23	11	0
Lanna research station	Sweden	SLU	X	Cattle manure	X	23		
TillComp (Ljubljana)	Slovenia	ULBF	X	Compost	X	25		0
BASIS	Netherlands	WUR	X			25	20	10

3. Biodiversity indicators and ecosystem functions

At each LTE we assessed several biodiversity indicators, encompassing all soil biota groups (microbiota, micro-, meso-, macro-fauna). Jointly we assessed multiple ecosystem functions that are known to be related, to different extents, to soil biota including regulation of soil organic carbon, nutrients, water and disease (Figure 3). Soil samples were extracted according to a common protocol that specified the location, depth and method for the soil extraction as well as the storage conditions Figure 4. Summary of the sampling scheme. Composite samples were composed of five subsamples mixed into a composite sample per plots. Soil blocks and infiltration were sampled at one sampling location per plot. Sample analyses was conducted collaboratively among MINOTAUR partners. Details on the sampling and quantification method can be found in MINOTAUR Deliverable 4.1.

Figure 3. Scheme of biodiversity indicators and ecosystem functions assessed for each LTE and treatment. The project partner conducting the analyses are indicated in brackets.

Figure 4. Summary of the sampling scheme. Composite samples were composed of five subsamples mixed into a composite sample per plots. Soil blocks and infiltration were sampled at one sampling location per plot.

4. Edaphoclimatic variation across LTEs

The Long-Term Experiments (LTEs) studied span a broad edaphoclimatic gradient, revealing significant variability in soil conditions and climatic factors (Table 2, Figure 5). Soil organic carbon and nitrogen content differ markedly among the LTEs, with Sweden (SLU) and Slovenia (ULBF) exhibiting the highest levels, while Spain (INIA) shows the lowest. Soil acidity also varies, with Boku, CREA, and Wageningen University & Research (WUR) having basic soils (pH 7-8) and higher nutrient availability, compared to the more acidic soils (pH 5-6) at ACO, SLU1, and AGS. Furthermore, soil structure shows notable differences, with SLU2 and ULBF having higher clay content (30-40%) than the other sites (13-20%). In terms of climate, SLU represents the coldest end of the spectrum with an average annual temperature around 6°C, while INIA and CREA, located in Mediterranean regions, experience warmer temperatures with annual averages of 13°C and maximum means around 24°C. The LTEs also vary in precipitation, with ULBF, AGS, and CREA receiving over 1000 mm annually, INIA the lowest at around 400 mm, and the rest falling between 500 and 800 mm. These variations in soil conditions and climate influence soil health, nutrient dynamics, and overall ecosystem functionality across the LTE sites.

Figure 5. Left, variation in mean annual temperatures and annual precipitation across the studied LTEs. Right, biplot resulted from a principal component analysis showing the covariation of soil attributes across the LTEs. Include Soil Organic Carbon, total N, Clay content, available nitrogen (NH4) available phosphorous and soil pH.

Table 2. General edaphoclimatic conditions (mean and (min, max)) across the studied LTEs. Include mean annual temperature (MAT) and cumulated annual precipitation, soil pH, soil organic carbon (SOC), soil total nitrogen (Total N), and clay content.

LTE	MAT (°C)	Precipitation (mm)	pH	SOC (%)	Total N (%)	Clay (%)	Sand
ACO	11.53 (5.48,18.36)	742 (46,86)	6.23 (5.7, 6.82)	1.36 (0.98, 1.91)	0.13 (0.1, 0.18)	13.1 (12.48, 13.48)	16.09 (13.74, 18.64)
AGS	9.26 (0.26,18.58)	1097 (70,120)	6.82 (4.91, 7.78)	1.82 (1.43, 2.38)	0.18 (0.14, 0.23)	19.27 (15.72, 23.75)	40.8 (36.62, 46.8)
BOKU	9.56 (-0.75,19.62)	535 (24,76)	8.27 (8.2, 8.36)	1.29 (0.82, 1.5)	0.14 (0.1, 0.16)	22.66 (20.82, 24.72)	27.87 (25.96, 29.8)
CREA	13.48 (4.55,23.27)	1056 (43,143)	8.47 (8.31, 8.59)	1.21 (1.04, 1.32)	0.12 (0.09, 0.14)	18.44 (15.02, 21.05)	45.26 (38.31, 54)
INIA	13.73 (5.04,24.32)	423 (10,60)	8.06 (7.44, 8.39)	0.87 (0.66, 1.08)	0.08 (0.05, 0.11)	20.23 (16.92, 24.72)	48.26 (41.86, 55.23)
SLU1	5.92 (-3.36,16.88)	575 (26,73)	5.36 (4.99, 5.75)	2.86 (2.39, 3.2)	0.22 (0.19, 0.24)	19.92 (17.68, 22.89)	38.83 (34.24, 42.42)
SLU2	6.57 (-2.15,16.4)	595 (27,70)	6.6 (6.16, 6.89)	2.02 (1.77, 2.37)	0.15 (0.13, 0.18)	41.63 (37.04, 45.14)	9.03 (8.16, 10.35)
ULBF	9.63 (-0.69,19.66)	1407 (72,163)	7.49 (6.98, 7.87)	2.23 (1.69, 3.42)	0.25 (0.18, 0.37)	31.52 (30.63, 32.98)	24.64 (22.96, 26.3)
WUR	9.64 (2.69,16.99)	776 (43,80)	8.46 (8.09, 8.54)	1.25 (0.81, 2.12)	0.11 (0.09, 0.13)	17.35 (16.78, 18.01)	56.51 (54.08, 58.49)

5. Soil biological indicators

5.1. Microbiota

Soil microbiota biomass indicators included bacterial and fungal biomass measured through the use of Fatty Acid Methyl Esters (FAMES), which are compounds derived from the esterification of fatty acids with methanol. FAMES are used as biomarkers for the presence of specific microbial groups and to assess microbial community structure. Additionally, ergosterol content was measured (de Ridder-Duine et al 2006). Ergosterol is a sterol found in the cell membranes of fungi and is critical for maintaining their structural integrity and functionality. Both bacterial and fungal biomass varied significantly across long-term experiments (LTE) and were sensitive to tillage practices Figure 6 Table 3. Microbial indicators estimated (mean and (min, max)) across the studied LTEs (acronyms are described in Table. 1.) Statistical differences across LTEs, Tillage and Fertilization treatment are noted below (**<math>0.001, **<math>0.01, *<math>0.05, · <math>0.1).. However, only bacterial biomass differed across fertilization treatments. In all cases, bacterial biomass was always larger than fungal biomass.

Figure 6. Variation on bacterial and fungal biomass across the studied LTEs.

Soil microbiota functional indicators included the copy numbers of functional genes such as the *phoD* gene, which encodes for an alkaline phosphatase enzyme involved in phosphorus acquisition by microorganisms. This enzyme hydrolyzes phosphate esters, releasing inorganic phosphate (Pi) from organic compounds, essential for microbial growth and metabolism. The *gcd* gene, which encodes for glucose dehydrogenase, facilitates the oxidation of glucose to gluconolactone, playing a significant role in microbial carbon utilization and organic matter degradation. Furthermore, the *amoA_bac* gene encodes the alpha-subunit of ammonia monooxygenase, an enzyme crucial for ammonia oxidation in bacteria. This gene is used as a marker to study the diversity and abundance of ammonia-oxidizing bacteria (AOB) in soil. Lastly, the *nirS* gene encodes for nitrite reductase, an enzyme involved in the

reduction of nitrite to nitric oxide during the denitrification pathway. This gene serves as a marker for denitrifying bacteria and is critical for understanding the processes of nitrogen removal and cycling in ecosystems.

Similar to the microbial biomass indicators, the abundances (copy numbers) of microbial functional genes varied significantly across the long-term experiments (LTEs), with all genes, except for phoD, showing variations related to tillage practices (although not in every LTE; Figure 7, Table 3). The gcd gene, which encodes glucose dehydrogenase, uniquely varied in response to fertilization. This variability is attributed to changes in substrate availability and shifts in microbial community composition. Increased nutrient inputs enhance the availability of glucose as a carbon source, promoting the proliferation of glucose-utilizing bacteria and leading to higher expression of the gcd gene.

Figure 7 Abundance (copy numbers) of the amoA gene of ammonia-oxidizing bacteria

Table 3. Microbial indicators estimated (mean and (min, max)) across the studied LTEs (acronyms are described in Table. 1.) Statistical differences across LTEs, Tillage and Fertilization treatment are noted below (***<0.001, **<0.01, *<0.05, ·<0.1).

LTE	Bacterial Biomass (nmol FAME ·g ⁻¹ soil)	Fungal Biomass (nmol FAME ·g ⁻¹ soil)	Ergosterol (µg ·g ⁻¹ soil)	PhoD (gene copy number ·g ⁻¹ soil)	Gcd (gene copy number ·g ⁻¹ soil)	amoA_bac (gene copy number ·g ⁻¹ soil)	NirS (gene copy number ·g ⁻¹ soil)
ACO	74.2 (47.9, 102.2)	26.6 (16.0, 39.8)	2,3E+08 (1.3E+08, 3.1E+08)	4,8E+11 (2.3E+11, 7.5E+11)	6,8E+09 (3.0E+09, 1.2E+09)	6,8E+10 (3.5E+10, 9.9E+10)	7,3E+08 (3.9E+08, 1.2E+08)

AGS	103 (69.7, 155.7)	29.2 (17.3, 44.7)	1, 0E+09 (1.0E+08, 7.3E+08)	8, 4E+11 (4.2E+11, 7.6E+11)	1, 9E+10 (3.0E+09, 9.1E+09)	1, 4E+11 (4.9E+10, 7.7E+10)	1, 6E+09 (2.0E+08, 9.5E+06)
BOKU	62.3 (39.4, 86.7)	17.8 (10.1, 26.1)	4, 1E+08 (1.7E+08, 8.4E+08)	3, 2E+11 (1.4E+11, 4.9E+11)	7, 5E+09 (3.1E+09, 2.8E+09)	4, 5E+10 (2.0E+10, 8.5E+10)	4, 9E+08 (1.3E+08, 9.3E+08)
CREA	37 (24.5, 54.9)	8.5 (4, 14.4)	4, 4E+08 (2.2E+08, 7.6E+08)	1, 9E+11 (7.8E+10, 2.8E+10)	3, 2E+09 (1.4E+09, 5.5E+09)	2, 8E+10 (1.1E+10, 4.8E+10)	2, 1E+08 (4.7E+07, 5.6E+07)
INIA	51.4 (28.1, 76.3)	13.5 (7.3, 19.2)	1, 9E+08 (5.1E+07, 3.7E+08)	2, 9E+11 (6.6E+10, 4.5E+10)	4, 6E+09 (1.9E+09, 7.8E+09)	3, 3E+10 (5.7E+09, 3.7E+09)	7, 7E+07 (1.2E+07, 1.6E+08)
SLU1	99.2 (78.2, 116)	24.4 (17.1, 30.9)	3, 3E+08 (1.4E+08, 5.8E+08)	7, 4E+11 (4.0E+11, 9.8E+11)	1, 9E+10 (7.2E+09, 2.9E+09)	1, 1E+11 (6.8E+10, 4.6E+10)	2, 0E+09 (8.4E+08, 8.8E+08)
SLU2	62.9 (51.4, 76.6)	13.7 (10.1, 18.1)	5, 4E+08 (2.5E+08, 1.5E+06)	4, 7E+11 (3.3E+11, 9.2E+11)	5, 8E+09 (4.1E+08, 5.6E+08)	7, 4E+10 (4.6E+10, 5.4E+09)	1, 2E+09 (7.9E+08, 4.0E+08)
ULBF	81.7 (50.2, 121.5)	20.2 (10.9, 28)	1, 6E+09 (5.7E+08, 8.0E+08)	6, 9E+11 (3.8E+11, 2.5E+11)	2, 2E+10 (5.5E+08, 3.5E+08)	1, 3E+11 (7.3E+10, 3.6E+10)	1, 9E+09 (7.8E+08, 3.4E+08)
WUR	39.3	13.2	8, 1E+08	3, 0E+11	5, 7E+09	4, 2E+10	2, 9E+08

Statistical differences

LTE ^a	***	***	***	***	***	***	***
Tillage ^b	***	*	**		***	***	**
Fertilization ^b	**				***		

^a Differences across LTE were tested using an Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) with LTE as treatment

^b Differences across Tillage treatments (Standard reduced, no tillage) or Fertilization treatment (Organic, Mineral, No fertilization) were tested using Linear Mixed Models, with LTE as a random factor, and Tillage and Fertilization as fixed factors.

5.2. Microfauna

Microfauna biomass indicators were assessed to evaluate soil health and microbial interactions, focusing on total nematode abundance and their functional group composition (Ferris et al, 2001; Figure 8). Total nematode abundance is reported as the number of individuals per 100 grams of dry soil, while the abundance is further categorized by functional groups, including herbivores, fungivores, bacterivores, predators, and omnivores. This classification provides insights into the trophic dynamics and ecological roles of nematodes within the soil ecosystem.

The abundance of nematodes varied across long-term experiments (LTEs), with LTEs such as ACO (France) and AGS (Switzerland) exhibiting the highest abundances of 5,586 and 4,311 individuals per 100 grams of dry soil, respectively, while CREA (Italy) recorded the lowest abundance at 172. Notably, there was a striking difference between the two LTEs located in Sweden, with SLU1 showing 4,176 nematodes and SLU2 showing only 367. Standard tillage practices generally resulted in lower nematode abundances. Additionally, the proportions of bacterivores and predators varied with tillage; however, no differences related to fertilization were observed, except for the proportion of fungivores.

Figure 8 Variation in total abundance of nematodes across LTEs and tillage treatments (ST – Standard tillage, RT – Reduced tillage, NT – No Tillage). LTE acronyms as in Table 1.

Nematode functional indicators were assessed using several indices. The Maturity Index (MI) measures environmental disturbance based on the composition of non-plant parasitic nematode species (Bongers, 1990). The Plant-Parasitic Index (PPI; Bongers, 1999) reflects the maturity of the root-feeding nematode community, which is determined by the vigor of their host plants and the level of system enrichment. Lastly, the Channel Index (CI; Ferris, 2001) serves as an indicator of the predominant decomposition pathways, distinguishing between bacterial and fungal decomposition. All indices varied across LTEs (Figure 9), but none responded to variation in management practices except for the Channel Index which was sensitive to changes in fertilization (Table 4).

Figure 9. Variation in Plant Parasitic Index across the studied LTEs. LTE acronyms as in Table 1. Plant-parasitic index (PPI) indicates the maturity of the root-feeding nematode community determined by the vigor of their host plants which, in turn, is determined by system enrichment

Table 4. Microfauna indicators estimated (mean and (min, max)) across the studied LTEs (acronyms are described in Table. 1.) Statistical differences across LTEs, Tillage and Fertilization treatment are noted below (***<0.001, **<0.01, *<0.05, ·<0.1).

LTE	Total abundance (ind· 100 g ⁻¹ soil)	Herbivores (%)	Fungivores (%)	Bacterivores (%)	Predators (%)	Omnivores (%)	Maturity Index ^a	Plant-parasitic index ^b	Channel Index ^c
ACO	5586 (3047, 7127)	20.2 (14.3, 31.3)	39.1 (32.9, 46.4)	37.3 (29.3, 42.8)	1 (0.2, 1.8)	2.3 (1, 4.2)	2 (2, 2.1)	2.4 (2.2, 2.6)	62.9 (43.4, 80.6)
AGS	4311 (1974, 10275)	20.5 (4.6, 35.5)	25.4 (14.2, 38.8)	45.2 (26.2, 75.5)	3.2 (0.5, 7.4)	5.6 (2.4, 9)	2 (1.4, 2.6)	2.5 (2.3, 2.7)	31 (5, 67.3)
BOKU	2083 (1080, 6724)	29.5 (6.8, 48.4)	25.4 (10.7, 39.6)	42 (25.2, 80.3)	1.6 (0.3, 4.3)	1.5 (0.4, 3)	1.9 (1.3, 2.1)	2.7 (2.4, 2.9)	38.6 (3.9, 70.2)
CREA	172 (40, 469)	23.2 (10.6, 29.3)	36.2 (14.9, 56.1)	33.6 (17.7, 51.1)	3.3 (0, 8.5)	3.8 (0, 9.8)	2.1 (1.8, 2.4)	2.2 (2.1, 2.4)	59.2 (9.9, 100)
INIA	2834 (730, 6555)	11.2 (3.4, 22.8)	45.7 (30.2, 58.9)	41 (30.8, 56.2)	0.1 (0, 0.3)	2 (0.6, 4.4)	1.9 (1.6, 2)	2.5 (2.2, 2.7)	63.1 (17.5, 93.7)
SLU1	4176 (2496, 8018)	24.5 (14.7, 38.9)	23.3 (11.8, 29.3)	48.2 (34.9, 70.2)	2.7 (1, 5.4)	1.2 (0.6, 3)	1.9 (1.7, 2.1)	2.6 (2.3, 2.8)	27.3 (7.3, 39.9)
SLU2	367 (246, 763)	28 (19.3, 37.8)	22.1 (6, 31.2)	21.6 (11.3, 32.5)	15 (5.9, 39.4)	13.3 (7.9, 23.5)	3.2 (2.6, 3.6)	2 (2, 2.1)	49.6 (18.7, 77.4)
ULBF	2728 (496, 6406)	9.1 (4.5, 15.1)	35.5 (21.4, 55.4)	47.9 (28.4, 65.9)	2.5 (0.6, 5)	4.7 (2.3, 8.6)	2 (1.8, 2.2)	2.3 (2.1, 2.6)	35.2 (12.2, 61.9)

WUR	943	1.3	26.3	72.1	0.3	0	1.7	2.3	17.5
	(490, 1329)	(0.3, 4.6)	(11.2, 43)	(56.3, 87.4)	(0, 1.5)	(0, 0.2)	(1.5, 1.8)	(2, 2.7)	(4.9, 31.3)
Statistical differences									
LTE ^a	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***
Tillage ^b	***	.	***	*					
Fertilization ^b			*	.					*

^a Differences across LTE were tested using an Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) with LTE as treatment

^b Differences across Tillage treatments (Standard reduced, no tillage) or Fertilization treatment (Organic, Mineral, No fertilization) were tested using Linear Mixed Models, with LTE as a random factor, and Tillage and Fertilization as fixed factors.

5.2.1. Mesofauna

Mesofauna biological indicators included the QBS-ar index (Parisi, 2001, 2005), which is a quantitative measure of soil biological quality based on the composition and abundance of soil arthropods that provides insights into soil health and ecosystem functioning (Table 5, Figure 10). This index is calculated by considering the presence of different functional groups of mesofauna, their ecological roles, and their response to environmental changes. A higher QBS-ar score indicates better soil quality, reflecting a more diverse and active soil community that contributes to essential soil processes such as nutrient cycling, organic matter decomposition, and soil structure maintenance.

In addition, we assessed the number of Eudaphic, Hemiedaphic, and Epigeic organisms, which represent different ecological groups of soil arthropods based on their habitat preferences and behavior (George et al, 2017). Eudaphic organisms are true soil-dwelling arthropods that reside exclusively in the soil or the deepest organic layers. They are highly adapted to life underground and are rarely found on the surface, with examples including certain mites and springtails. In contrast, Hemiedaphic arthropods inhabit both the soil and the surface, capable of moving between soil layers and the litter layer, exhibiting intermediate adaptations to both environments. Lastly, Epigeic organisms are surface-dwelling arthropods that primarily inhabit the litter layer on top of the soil and seldom burrow into deeper layers. These arthropods are adapted to life on the soil surface or in decaying organic matter.

All four indicators varied across LTEs, although the QBS-ar showed the strongest response and was the only indicator that also varied with tillage treatment. None responded to fertilization.

Figure 10. Variation in the QBS-ar index across LTEs. LTE acronyms as in Table 1. The QBS-ar (Soil Biological Quality - arthropods) index is used to assess soil biodiversity by quantifying the abundance and diversity of edaphic arthropods, with higher values indicating greater environmental quality and ecological stability.

Table 5. Mesofauna (microarthropods) indicators estimated (mean and (min, max)) across the studied LTEs (acronyms are described in Table. 1.) Statistical differences across LTEs, Tillage and Fertilization treatment are noted below (***<0.001, **<0.01, *<0.05, · <0.1).

LTE	QBS_ar	Eudaphic (number biological forms)	Emiedaphic (number biological forms)	Epigeic (number biological forms)
ACO	114.5 (112, 118)	4 (4, 4)	2.8 (2, 3)	3 (2, 4)
AGS	141 (131, 156)	4.8 (4, 6)	4 (3, 5)	2 (1, 3)
BOKU	92.3 (86, 96)	3 (3, 3)	2.7 (2, 3)	1.7 (1, 2)
CREA	102.5 (77, 128)	3.5 (2, 5)	2.5 (2, 3)	3.5 (3, 4)
INIA	93.8 (62, 122)	2.8 (1, 5)	2.2 (1, 3)	4.2 (4, 5)
SLU1	112.7 (103, 118)	4.7 (4, 5)	1.3 (1, 2)	3.3 (3, 4)
SLU2	65.7 (52, 82)	2.7 (2, 3)	1 (0, 2)	2.3 (2, 3)
WUR	73.7 (62, 88)	2.7 (2, 3)	1.7 (1, 2)	2.3 (1, 4)

Statistical differences				
LTE ^a	***	**	*	**
Tillage ^b	*			
Fertilization ^b				

^a Differences across LTE were tested using an Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) with LTE as treatment

^b Differences across Tillage treatments (Standard reduced, no tillage) or Fertilization treatment (Organic, Mineral, No fertilization) were tested using Linear Mixed Models, with LTE as a random factor, and Tillage and Fertilization as fixed factors

5.3. Macrofauna

Macrofauna indicators were utilized to evaluate soil health and ecosystem functioning (Lagerlöf & Lagerlöf, 2002; Paoletti, 1999), focusing on various metrics such as total biomass (g·m²), total abundance (individuals·m²), species richness, and the Shannon index. Total biomass represents the overall weight of macrofauna per unit area, while total abundance indicates the number of individual organisms present in the same area. Species richness provides insight into the diversity of species present, and the Shannon index measures the evenness of species distribution within the community. Additionally, the abundance of specific ecological functional groups was assessed, including epigeic species (surface-dwelling organisms), anecic species (deep burrowers), epianecic species (organisms that inhabit both surface and deeper soil layers), and endogeic species (those primarily living within the soil; Lavelle and Spain: 2001).

Indicators related to biomass or abundances and diversity varied significantly across LTEs and tillage practice. Mirroring the observed variation with the microfauna (nematodes) and to a certain extent with the microbial biomass, CREA (Italy) showed notably smaller biomass values than other sites (Figure 11, Figure 12, Table 6). It is also relevant to highlight that INIA (Spain) reported no earthworms collected during the sampling. The absence of earthworms in Mediterranean sites can be attributed to several ecological and environmental factors, including unfavorable soil characteristics, such as high clay content and low organic matter, which limit their survival and reproduction. The hot, dry summers typical of Mediterranean climates create extended periods of low moisture availability, making it challenging for earthworms to thrive. Agricultural practices and land disturbances can disrupt soil structure and compaction, hindering earthworm movement and population density. Collectively, these factors can contribute to the limited occurrence of earthworms in Mediterranean agroecosystems, where alternative soil organisms (e.g. ants) may play more significant roles in nutrient cycling and soil structure.

Figure 11. Variation in earthworm biomass (g/m²) across LTEs and tillage treatment. Black diamond shows mean value per LTE. ST – Standard tillage, RT – Reduced tillage, NT – No Tillage. LTE acronyms as in Table 1.

The functional indicators used for macrofauna, specifically the proportional abundance of different ecological groups, varied across the long-term experiments (LTEs), reflecting the distinct functional composition of the earthworm community along the edaphoclimatic gradient. Endogeic species were the most abundant in all sites; however, CREA exhibited a significant proportional abundance of deep burrowing species at 30%. In contrast, in the other sites, the second most abundant group comprised epianecic species, which inhabit both surface and deeper soil layers. These functional indicators were mostly not sensitive to changes in management practices.

Figure 12. Variation in earthworm species richness across the studied LTEs. LTE acronyms as in Table 1.

Table 6. Macrofauna (earthworms) indicators estimated (mean and (min, max)) across the studied LTEs (acronyms are described in Table. 1.) Statistical differences across LTEs, Tillage and Fertilization treatment are noted below (***<0.001, **<0.01, *<0.05, · <0.1).

LTE	Total biomass (g · m ⁻²)	Total abundance (individual · m ⁻²)	Species Richness	Shannon index	Abundance of epigeic spp (%)	Abundance of anecic strict spp (%)	Abundance of anecic spp (%)	Abundance of epianecic spp (%)	Abundance of endogeic spp (%)
ACO	50.2 (33.1, 87.1)	250 (166.7, 550)	4.8 (3, 6)	1.8 (1, 2.1)	0.9 (0, 4)	6.9 (0, 19.2)	0 (0, 0)	13.6 (0, 29.2)	78.7 (50, 100)
AGS	80.5 (21.7, 158.8)	212 (100, 358.3)	6 (4, 8)	2.3 (1.6, 2.7)	0 (0, 0)	12.2 (0, 32.1)	0 (0, 0)	18.1 (3.1, 44.4)	69.7 (50, 90.7)
CREA	4 (0.3, 6.8)	26.7 (8.3, 50)	1.6 (1, 2)	0.5 (0, 0.9)	0 (0, 0)	0 (0, 0)	30 (0, 100)	0 (0, 0)	70 (0, 100)
INIA	0 (0, 0)	0 (0, 0)	0 (0, 0)	0 (0, 0)	0 (0, 0)	0 (0, 0)	0 (0, 0)	0 (0, 0)	0 (0, 0)
SLU1	82.5 (34.7, 157.9)	240.7 (150, 350)	5.1 (3, 6)	1.8 (0.6, 2.4)	1.1 (0, 10)	4 (0, 23.3)	0 (0, 0)	11.5 (0, 30.4)	83.4 (53.3, 100)
SLU2	64.7 (30, 123.9)	287.5 (150, 575)	3.8 (1, 6)	1.3 (0, 1.8)	0.7 (0, 8.3)	0 (0, 0)	0 (0, 0)	16.2 (0, 40)	83.1 (60, 100)
ULBF	25.5 (3.8, 80.6)	81.7 (33.3, 158.3)	2.8 (1, 5)	1 (0, 1.8)	0 (0, 0)	0 (0, 0)	0 (0, 0)	1.7 (0, 12.5)	98.3 (87.5, 100)
WUR	11.9 (1.6, 23.6)	68.8 (16.7, 141.7)	2.5 (1, 3)	0.9 (0, 1.4)	5.4 (0, 33.3)	0 (0, 0)	0 (0, 0)	4.3 (0, 20)	90.3 (66.7, 100)
Statistical differences									
LTE ^a	***	***	***	***	.	***	***	***	***
Tillage ^b	***	*	***	***		**			
Fertilization ^b	*								

^a Differences across LTE were tested using an Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) with LTE as treatment

^b Differences across Tillage treatments (Standard reduced, no tillage) or Fertilization treatment (Organic, Mineral, No fertilization) were tested using Linear Mixed Models, with LTE as a random factor, and Tillage and Fertilization as fixed factors.

6. Soil functions

6.1. Regulation of soil organic carbon and nutrients

A wide range of indicators was employed to assess variations in soil functions related to the regulation of soil organic carbon and nutrient cycling (Table 7, Table 8). These indicators included measurements of soil carbon concentrations and nutrient levels in their total organic, inorganic, or available forms (Sparling et al 1998). Microbial respiration was evaluated as a proxy to account for overall soil microbial activity, providing insights into the biological processes occurring within the soil matrix.

Additionally, the activity of specific enzymes was assessed to determine variations in the soil's cycling capacity, as each enzyme plays a crucial role in nutrient availability and transformation (Table 9; García et al., 2003; Nannipieri et al 1980; Tabatai & Bremner, 1970; Tabatai 1994; Trasar-Cepeda et al, 2008).

Dehydrogenase ($\mu\text{mol INT g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$) serves as an indicator of microbial oxidative activity and overall soil health, reflecting the potential for microbial respiration and organic matter decomposition. Urease ($\mu\text{mol NH}_3 \text{g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$) catalyzes the hydrolysis of urea into ammonia and carbon dioxide, facilitating nitrogen cycling and making nitrogen available for plant uptake. Aryl-sulfatase ($\mu\text{mol p-nitrophenol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$) is involved in the mineralization of organic sulfur compounds, enabling the release of sulfate, an essential nutrient for plant growth. Acid phosphomonoesterase ($\mu\text{mol p-nitrophenol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$) hydrolyzes organic phosphates, enhancing phosphorus availability in acidic soils, which is critical for plant development. In contrast, alkaline phosphomonoesterase ($\mu\text{mol p-nitrophenol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$) operates optimally in alkaline conditions, assisting in the mobilization of phosphorus from organic sources. Lastly, β -glucosidase ($\mu\text{mol p-nitrophenol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$) catalyzes the hydrolysis of glycosidic bonds in carbohydrates, significantly contributing to the decomposition of plant materials and the release of sugars for microbial uptake. Collectively, the assessment of these indicators provides a comprehensive understanding of soil health and the efficiency of nutrient cycling processes, highlighting the intricate interactions between biological and chemical factors that contribute to soil fertility and ecosystem functioning.

All estimated parameters varied significantly across LTEs, and in most cases also varied with agricultural management treatment (tillage and fertilization: (Table 7, Table 8, 9) with few exceptions such as the macronutrients (Ca, K, Mg).

Table 7. Estimated indicators related to soil carbon and nitrogen (mean and (min, max)) across the studied LTEs (acronyms are described in Table. 1.) Statistical differences across LTEs, Tillage and Fertilization treatment are noted below (***<0.001, **<0.01, *<0.05, ·<0.1).

LTE	Total C (%)	Organic C (%)	Total N (%)	Corg / N	Labile C (mg kg ⁻¹)	d ¹³ C (‰)	d ¹⁵ N (‰)
ACO	1.4 (1, 1.9)	1.4 (1, 1.9)	0.1 (0.1, 0.2)	10.7 (10, 11.4)	858 (599.8, 1254.2)	-25.8 (-26.1, -25.4)	5.9 (1.8, 8.7)
AGS	2 (1.4, 3.1)	1.8 (1.4, 2.4)	0.2 (0.1, 0.2)	10.3 (7.8, 11.7)	1935.3 (1547.3, 2294.7)	-26.8 (-27.6, -25.5)	4.1 (2.5, 8)
BOKU	2.7 (2.3, 3.1)	1.3 (0.8, 1.5)	0.1 (0.1, 0.2)	9.5 (8.3, 10.5)	606.9 (417.2, 737.4)	-24.6 (-25.3, -24.4)	3.5 (2.2, 4.8)
CREA	1.4 (1.1, 1.7)	1.2 (1, 1.3)	0.1 (0.1, 0.1)	10.7 (8.3, 13.8)	417.9 (270.8, 546.4)	-22.5 (-26.8, -19.7)	3.1 (1.8, 4.3)
INIA	0.9 (0.7, 1.6)	0.9 (0.7, 1.1)	0.1 (0.1, 0.1)	11.8 (9.6, 20.1)	583.4 (393.8, 817.4)	-25.3 (-26, -24.6)	3.8 (-1.3, 9.2)
SLU1	2.9 (2.4, 3.2)	2.9 (2.4, 3.2)	0.2 (0.2, 0.2)	13 (12.4, 14.1)	1340 (1073.5, 1540.6)	-27.6 (-28.1, -27.4)	5 (3.2, 7.6)
SLU2	2 (1.8, 2.4)	2 (1.8, 2.4)	0.2 (0.1, 0.2)	13.5 (12.5, 14.9)	820.3 (605, 1616.9)	-27.5 (-27.8, -27.1)	4.2 (3.3, 5.7)
ULBF	2.8 (1.9, 4.4)	2.2 (1.7, 3.4)	0.3 (0.2, 0.4)	8.9 (8.3, 9.5)	906.5 (616.7, 1395.5)	-25.2 (-25.8, -24.1)	3.9 (2.4, 5.3)
WUR	1.9 (1.7, 2.1)	1.2 (0.8, 2.1)	0.1 (0.1, 0.1)	11.2 (9.1, 18.5)	556.1 (372, 688.5)	-26.9 (-28, -26.2)	3.8 (2.1, 6)
Statistical differences							

LTE ^a	***	***	***	***	***	***	**
Tillage ^b	***	***	***	*	***		
Fertilization ^b	***	***	***		*		***

^a Differences across LTE were tested using an Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) with LTE as treatment

^b Differences across Tillage treatments (Standard reduced, no tillage) or Fertilization treatment (Organic, Mineral, No fertilization) were tested using Linear Mixed Models, with LTE as a random factor, and Tillage and Fertilization as fixed factors.

Figure 13. Variation in total organic carbon across LTEs and tillage treatments (ST – Standard tillage, RT – Reduced tillage, NT – No Tillage). LTE acronyms as in Table 1.

Table 8. Soil nutrients indicators (mean and (min, max)) across the studied LTEs (acronyms are described in Table. 1.) Statistical differences across LTEs, Tillage and Fertilization treatment are noted below (***<0.001, **<0.01, *<0.05, ·<0.1).

LTE	Available Pi (mg kg ⁻¹)	NH ₄ (mg kg ⁻¹)	NO ₃ (mg kg ⁻¹)	P (mg kg ⁻¹)	Ca (mg kg ⁻¹)	K (mg kg ⁻¹)	Mg (mg kg ⁻¹)
ACO	122.4 (90.4, 150.9)	0.3 (0, 0.6)	46.6 (0, 83)	648.4 (571.8, 704)	1974.5 (1750.4, 2374.5)	4935.4 (4549.2, 5350.8)	1943.8 (1855.2, 2092)
AGS	27.2 (16.2, 51.4)	0.8 (0.2, 3.3)	66.9 (27.5, 123.5)	558.1 (481.1, 672.5)	6273.7 (2218.3, 19893.3)	7116.8 (6192, 8964.4)	5859.5 (4368.8, 9575.2)
BOKU	25.4 (20.7, 29.5)	0.1 (0, 0.3)	12 (0, 18.2)	685.1 (658.8, 730.2)	42696.6 (37283.6, 47863.7)	7057.3 (6317, 7354.9)	8460.5 (8052.6, 8762.3)

CREA	63.1 (46.4, 101.9)	0.2 (0, 0.5)	22.9 (12.1, 34.9)	829.9 (663.9, 1026)	18923.1 (9618.4, 32087.7)	9414.2 (8490.3, 10323.7)	7569.1 (6097.2, 8720.5)
INIA	20.6 (7.6, 48.2)	0.2 (0, 1.2)	26.8 (13.2, 45.3)	323 (236.9, 494.6)	9138.3 (3000.6, 49798.5)	7541.7 (6742.9, 8914.9)	4299.5 (3451.6, 5862.1)
SLU1	41.9 (27.4, 60.4)	0.5 (0.4, 0.8)	73.3 (43.1, 102)	745 (709.8, 802.2)	6524.9 (6251.6, 6868.1)	5184.4 (4735.2, 5900.8)	4528.6 (4162.8, 5007.9)
SLU2	64.3 (44.4, 102.2)	0.4 (0.2, 0.5)	19.7 (13.9, 29.5)	617.9 (549.9, 749.6)	6318.1 (5835.2, 6583)	6754.1 (6089.4, 7267.3)	4204.3 (3899.5, 4505.6)
ULBF	65.9 (25.6, 127.9)	0.2 (0, 0.8)	30.2 (0, 57.5)	684.4 (500.2, 965.1)	5123.5 (3282.9, 8827.5)	8932 (8034.4, 9861.8)	4295.7 (3824.3, 4769.5)
WUR	65.3 (39.9, 100.4)	0.2 (0, 0.3)	16 (3, 30)	477 (426.9, 541.7)	25968.2 (24241, 27843.9)	5874.9 (5430.9, 6205.7)	4641.1 (4394.5, 4766.3)
Statistical differences							
LTE ^a	***	***	***	***	***	***	***
Tillage ^b	*	**	***	***	.		
Fertilization ^b	*		*	***			

^a Differences across LTE were tested using an Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) with LTE as treatment

^b Differences across Tillage treatments (Standard reduced, no tillage) or Fertilization treatment (Organic, Mineral, No fertilization) were tested using Linear Mixed Models, with LTE as a random factor, and Tillage and Fertilization as fixed factors.

Figure 14. Variation in available ammonia (NO_3) across LTEs and tillage treatments (ST – Standard tillage, RT – Reduced tillage, NT – No Tillage). LTE acronyms as in Table 1.

Figure 15. Variation in basal soil respiration across LTEs and tillage treatments (ST – Standard tillage, RT – Reduced tillage, NT – No Tillage). LTE acronyms as in Table 1.

Table 9. Soil activity indicators (mean and (min, max)) across the studied LTEs (acronyms are described in Table. 1.) Statistical differences across LTE, Tillage and Fertilization treatment are noted below (***) <math><0.001</math>, (**) <math><0.01</math>, (*) <math><0.05</math>, \cdot <math><0.1</math>).

LTE	Basal soil respiration ($\mu\text{g C-CO}_2$ soil g^{-1} day $^{-1}$)	Dehydrogenase ($\mu\text{mol INTF g}^{-1}$ h^{-1})	Urease ($\mu\text{mol NH}_3 \text{g}^{-1}$ h^{-1})	Arylsulphatase ($\mu\text{mol p-}$ nitrophenol g^{-1} h^{-1})	Acid phosphomono- esterase ($\mu\text{mol p-}$ nitrophenol g^{-1} h^{-1})	Alkaline phosphomon- oesterase ($\mu\text{mol p-}$ nitrophenol g^{-1} h^{-1})	β -glucosidase ($\mu\text{mol p-}$ nitrophenol g^{-1} h^{-1})
ACO	8.4 (5.4, 10.5)	0.3 (0.2, 0.5)	3.1 (2, 4.9)	0.1 (0.1, 0.2)	2.2 (1.8, 2.5)	0.5 (0.2, 0.9)	0.6 (0.4, 0.8)
AGS	10.3 (7.2, 15.4)	0.5 (0.2, 0.8)	4.5 (2.3, 8.2)	0.2 (0.1, 0.4)	2.1 (1.2, 3.2)	2.1 (0.4, 3.6)	1.1 (0.8, 1.5)
BOKU	6 (3.7, 8)	0.3 (0.2, 0.3)	3 (1.6, 4)	0.1 (0, 0.1)	0.6 (0.3, 0.9)	2.4 (1.6, 3.1)	0.9 (0.6, 1.1)
CREA	4 (2.4, 5.5)	0.2 (0.1, 0.3)	1.5 (0.8, 2.4)	0.1 (0, 0.1)	0.3 (0.2, 0.4)	1.6 (1, 2.3)	0.6 (0.3, 0.9)
INIA	5.9 (3.5, 10.4)	0.3 (0.2, 0.4)	1.9 (0.9, 5)	0 (0, 0.1)	0.3 (0.2, 0.9)	1.5 (0.9, 2)	0.9 (0.3, 1.4)
SLU1	9.6 (7.5, 11.3)	0.3 (0.3, 0.4)	3.3 (2.7, 3.7)	0 (0, 0.1)	3.9 (3.3, 4.7)	0.5 (0.3, 0.6)	1 (0.7, 1.2)
SLU2	6.8	0.2	3.3	0.1	1.8	0.9	0.6

	(5.3, 8.9)	(0.2, 0.3)	(2.6, 4.4)	(0.1, 0.1)	(1.5, 2.2)	(0.6, 1.2)	(0.5, 0.8)
ULBF	10.1	0.3	6	0.2	1.1	2.1	0.8
	(6, 15.8)	(0.2, 0.6)	(3.9, 9.7)	(0.2, 0.3)	(0.7, 1.7)	(1.1, 3.1)	(0.5, 1.2)
WUR	6.8	0.3	2.5	0.1	0.6	2.2	0.7
	(3.8, 10.2)	(0.2, 0.4)	(1.3, 4.7)	(0.1, 0.1)	(0.4, 0.7)	(1.5, 2.8)	(0.4, 1)
Statistical differences							
LTE ^a	***	***	***	***	***	***	***
Tillage ^b	***	***	***	**	***	***	***
Fertilization ^b	**	**	**	***		*	***

^a Differences across LTE were tested using an Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) with LTE as treatment

^b Differences across Tillage treatments (Standard reduced, no tillage) or Fertilization treatment (Organic, Mineral, No fertilization) were tested using Linear Mixed Models, with LTE as a random factor, and Tillage and Fertilization as fixed factors.

6.2. Regulation of water

Soil functions related to the regulation of water are critical for maintaining ecosystem health, agricultural productivity, and managing water resources. Various indicators have been utilized to assess soil's capacity to retain and transmit water. Mean Weight Diameter after Fast Wetting (MWD_FW) is measured in millimeters and evaluates soil aggregate stability after a rapid wetting test, simulating the impact of intense rainfall (Gee & Bauder, 1986; Le Bissonnais 1996). Higher MWD_FW values indicate more stable aggregates that resist breakdown during heavy rainfall, while lower values suggest increased susceptibility to erosion. Mean Weight Diameter after Mechanical Breakdown (MWD_MB) assesses aggregate stability following mechanical disturbance, providing insights into how well soil maintains its structure when subjected to physical forces, such as tillage. Higher MWD_MB values reflect greater aggregate stability, essential for understanding soil resilience. Additionally, Mean Weight Diameter after Slow Wetting (MWD_SW) measures aggregate stability under gradual moisture infiltration, with higher values indicating better resistance to breakdown during typical moisture scenarios like light rain. The term S (Soil sorptivity) quantifies the ability of the soil to absorb water due to capillary suction and is a function of the initial soil moisture (Philip, 1957). The term Ksat (hydraulic conductivity at saturation), defines the phase of the infiltration curve where infiltration over time stabilizes, also referred to as saturated infiltration rate. Ksat, being less dependent on initial soil moisture, is used as a standardized measure to compare infiltration rates between sites and is expressed in millimeters per hour (mm h⁻¹). These metrics are critical for evaluating how quickly water moves through saturated soils, influencing practices related to irrigation, drainage, and overall water management in agricultural and natural ecosystems. Collectively, these indicators provide valuable insights into soil structure, stability, and the ability to regulate water, which is essential for sustaining plant growth and preventing erosion.

Similar to the indicators for soil carbon and nutrient regulators, all estimated indicators varied significantly across land treatment experiments (LTEs) and were influenced by management practices, including tillage and fertilization (Table 10, Figure 16).

Table 10. Soil aggregate stability and infiltration indicators estimated (mean and (min, max)) across the studied LTEs (acronyms are described in Table. 1.) MWD_FW - Mean Weight Diameter after Fast Wetting. MWD_MB - Mean Weight Diameter after Mechanical Breakdown. MWD_SW - Mean Weight Diameter after Slow Wetting. S - soil sorptivity, Ksat - hydraulic conductivity at saturation Statistical differences across LTEs , Tillage and Fertilization treatment are noted below (***<0.001, **<0.01, *<0.05, · <0.1).

LTE	MWD_FW (mm)	MWD_MB (mm)	MWD_SW (mm)	MWD_mean (mm)	Infiltration rate (cm h ⁻¹)	S (mm h ⁻¹)	Ksat (mm h ⁻¹)
ACO	0.57 (0.38, 0.82)	1.34 (0.93, 1.83)	1.17 (0.53, 1.64)	1.03 (0.62, 1.34)	8.94 (2.29, 12.36)	0.1 (-0.01, 0.16)	66.87 (19.8, 99.36)
AGS	1.21 (0.8, 1.76)	2.12 (1.58, 2.6)	2.3 (1.23, 3.03)	1.88 (1.21, 2.45)	15.97 (6.74, 37.56)	0.09 (0.02, 0.2)	119.08 (52.92, 225)
BOKU	0.54 (0.28, 0.89)	1.8 (1.16, 2.13)	1.1 (0.45, 1.99)	1.15 (0.63, 1.67)	3.28 (1.09, 6.13)	0.06 (0.03, 0.08)	25.66 (10.8, 49.68)
CREA	0.52 (0.37, 0.72)	1.09 (0.75, 1.23)	0.61 (0.46, 1.02)	0.74 (0.56, 0.99)	3.45 (1.28, 5.09)	0.06 (0.03, 0.09)	20.27 (2.88, 38.88)
INIA	0.4 (0.25, 0.81)	0.43 (0.33, 0.66)	0.63 (0.32, 1.59)	0.49 (0.32, 1.02)	13.17 (1.99, 44.37)	0.07 (0.02, 0.26)	113.11 (15.48, 378)
SLU1	0.98 (0.5, 1.66)	2.07 (1.46, 2.81)	2.56 (1.79, 3.12)	1.87 (1.36, 2.4)	9.22 (2.21, 22.07)	0.09 (0.01, 0.15)	79.79 (19.8, 190.8)
SLU2	0.49 (0.39, 0.65)	2.75 (2.22, 3.04)	1.59 (1.11, 2.37)	1.61 (1.27, 1.91)	25.94 (1.27, 70.55)	0.22 (0.02, 0.37)	170.64 (11.52, 763.56)
ULBF	0.92 (0.58, 1.5)	2.86 (2.62, 3.11)	1.51 (0.95, 2.21)	1.76 (1.45, 2.22)	No data	No data	No data
WUR	0.35 (0.29, 0.41)	0.86 (0.68, 1.01)	0.64 (0.41, 0.9)	0.62 (0.55, 0.73)	25.24 (2.14, 115)	0.11 (-0.11, 0.42)	117.72 (11.52, 489.24)
Statistical differences							
LTE ^a	***	***	***	***	***	***	***
Tillage ^b	***	***	***	***	***	***	*
Fertilization ^b	***	***	***	***	**	**	***

^a Differences across LTE were tested using an Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) with LTE as treatment

^b Differences across Tillage treatments (Standard reduced, no tillage) or Fertilization treatment (Organic, Mineral, No fertilization) were tested using Linear Mixed Models, with LTE as a random factor, and Tillage and Fertilization as fixed factors.

Figure 16. Variation in aggregate stability across LTEs and tillage treatments (ST – Standard tillage, RT – Reduced tillage, NT – No Tillage). Diamond represent mean value for each LTE. LTE acronyms as in Table 1.

Figure 17. Variation in infiltration rate across LTEs and tillage treatments (ST – Standard tillage, RT – Reduced tillage, NT – No Tillage). Diamond represent mean value for each LTE. LTE acronyms as in Table 1.

6.2.1. Disease suppression

Soil disease suppressiveness is a vital function of soil health, reflecting the soil's ability to inhibit the establishment and spread of plant pathogens. This capacity is crucial for promoting sustainable agricultural practices and enhancing plant health (Van Bruggen et al, 2000). In assessing soil disease suppressiveness, the inoculation with *Pythium*, a common soil-borne pathogen, serves as a valuable method for evaluating soil's capacity to mitigate pathogen infection in plants. This approach involves introducing *Pythium* into the soil and observing the subsequent effects on plant health and disease incidence. A more suppressive soil environment will show reduced levels of pathogen infection, indicating the presence of beneficial microbial communities or soil properties that enhance disease resistance.

The soil's capacity for disease suppression, calculated as the difference between the natural levels of non-inoculated plants and the values observed in inoculated plants for plant cover and biomass production, varied across LTEs. Significant differences were found among LTEs and tillage treatments, while no effect was observed with fertilization.

Table 11. Indicators of soil disease suppression capacity (mean and (min, max)) across the studied LTEs (acronyms are described in Table. 1.) The percentage of plant cover affected by infection is calculated by subtracting the plant cover in non-inoculated pots (representing the natural degree of infection) from the plant cover in pots inoculated with the pathogen (*Pythium*). Plant biomass loss due to infection is calculated by subtracting the plant biomass in pots inoculated with the pathogen from the plant cover in non-inoculated pots. Statistical differences across LTEs, Tillage and Fertilization treatment are noted below (***<0.001, **<0.01, *<0.05, · <0.1).

LTE	Plant cover affected by infection (%)	Plant biomass loss due to infection (g)
ACO	16.21 (0, 51.25)	0.17 (0, 0.55)
AGS	64.09 (33, 83.75)	1.49 (0.51, 2.72)
BOKU	71.33 (51.25, 82.5)	1.79 (0.74, 2.59)
CREA	65.83 (31.25, 90)	1.5 (0.26, 2.65)
INIA	5.62 (0, 62.5)	0.48 (0, 2.72)
SLU1	15.81 (3, 27.75)	0.25 (0.11, 0.5)
SLU2	16.67 (10.75, 23)	0.2 (0.13, 0.32)
ULBF	0 (0, 57.5)	0.07 (0, 1.56)
WUR	86.32 (82.5, 92.5)	1.99 (1.25, 2.83)
LTE ^a	***	***
Tillage ^b	**	**
Fertilization ^b		

^a Differences across LTE were tested using an Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) with LTE as treatment

^b Differences across Tillage treatments (Standard reduced, no tillage) or Fertilization treatment (Organic, Mineral, No fertilization) were tested using Linear Mixed Models, with LTE as a random factor, and Tillage and Fertilization as fixed factors.

Figure 18. Variation in healthy (not affected) plant cover after inoculation with soil pathogen (*Pythium*) across LTEs and tillage treatments (ST – Standard tillage, RT – Reduced tillage, NT – No Tillage). Diamond represent mean value for each LTE. LTE acronyms as in Table 1.

7. Conclusions

This deliverable has provided an overview of the variation observed in several biological indicators related to the abundance, taxonomic diversity, and functional diversity of microbiota, as well as micro, meso-, and macrofauna across nine different long-term experiments (LTEs) located throughout the EU, all subjected to comparable tillage and fertilization treatments. In addition to these biological indicators, four key soil functions—carbon regulation, nutrient cycling, water regulation, and soil disease suppression—have been assessed through multiple parameters.

The results emphasize that the primary source of variation in soil health indicators, particularly those related to soil biodiversity and functioning, is attributed to the differences observed across the LTEs. This finding underscores the significance of geographical variations in soil conditions and climate, which in turn influence soil diversity and functioning. Furthermore, tillage practices (standard, reduced, and no tillage) emerged as the second most important factor driving variation within the LTEs. However, the effects of tillage were inconsistent across sites, indicating a complex interplay between soil management practices and local conditions that warrants further investigation. In contrast, there was considerably less variation associated with fertilization treatments (mineral, organic, and no fertilization), suggesting that their impact on soil biodiversity and functioning may be less significant compared to other factors.

These findings highlight the varying capacities of the studied indices to reflect changes in management practices and contribute to the establishment of locally adapted reference values based on edaphoclimatic conditions. Ultimately, this work aims to guide the selection of the most sensitive indicators for implementation in soil health monitoring programs.

8. Data repository

Data will be made available in an open permanent repository ZENODO under the community MINOTAUR <https://zenodo.org/communities/minotaur>. Data will follow the FAIR principles: Findable, Interoperable, Accessible and Reusable. Datasets will have their own DOI, which will be referenced in scientific publications, under a CC BY license (open with recognition of authorship). Data will become available at the end of the project, respecting an embargo period to get results published. Intellectual properties rights will be respected.

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